

Interview with the Healthcare Engineering Unit (HCEU) architect and engineer, involved in the construction of the new District Hospitals.

30th July 2024.

The conversation took place at 9:00am at the HCEU in Zanzibar in English. The architect and engineer's answers have been combined and summarised for clarity. The summarised interview was sent back to the engineer at HCEU to ensure the condensed answers accurately communicated what was discussed at the interview.

Can you describe a little about the design process for the District Hospitals?

The original designer is now retired, having left in February 2024. We assisted on the construction and design details during the construction process.

The design was produced very fast and funded by a Loan from IMF for COVID relief money. There was only 2 months for design and no brief given. The President of Zanzibar is a doctor by profession and is pushing better healthcare system through improving the infrastructure. Zanzibar is trying to copy what the mainland is doing, where patients first go to the PHCUs and then are referred to the district, regional or referral hospitals if they need further care. Before this, most people were going directly to the referral hospital.

One of the doctors in Kivunge said this is still happening in Kivunge, where mainly patients are coming directly to the hospital which should have gone to the PHCUs first, which means the waiting area is very busy.

Yes this is the case as the PHCUs have not been upgraded yet. We have drawn the designs for the new PHCUs and construction is beginning on these.

To develop the design, engineers produced sketches and showed them to a panel of doctors, who were heads of departments within the existing healthcare system, to get feedback from them on the proposal. Given the short deadline there was little time for collaboration.

Feedback points were mostly concerning the programming of the hospital. Examples discussed included:

- Feedback on Emergency to ensure there is a porched receival area and special stretchers bay
- Space for patient triage
- Primary Health Care Units only had 1 lab, which was often not enough, so the District hospitals included x2 laboratory rooms
- Create separate spaces for medical storage and dispensary

What was the inspiration behind the design of the hospital?

Inspired by stone town architecture, which is adapted from the traditional Omani architecture. This is unique to Stone Town. This can be seen, for example, in the arched main entrance.

What was the process for the choice of materials for the hospitals?

The main drivers for materials and building component choice were cost, availability and what people in Zanzibar are used to. For example concrete block was chosen for the walls as this is cheap and readily available here. Another examples was the choice of windows. We did not use hinged windows because people are not used to operating them so they are likely to break them. We were also concerned that they might be broken by the wind if left open.

Can you describe the sustainability strategy for the building design?

We tried to choose materials that would last a long time. For example, early on we were thinking to use ceramic tiles for the flooring as they are easy to clean, however we were concerned about the longevity of the tiles over tile. So instead we decided to use terrazzo flooring which is longer lasting. This however had some other challenges as we could not get the proper materials for waterproofing the terrazzo. So in some of the wet areas we used tiles on the floor and walls.

How did you consider how the design of the hospitals can reduce disease transmission in the hospitals themselves?

The introduction of the triage area was part of this strategy. This was designed to be the first place patients visited, to establish what the health issue was. If patients had diseases that can be transmitted easily they are separated.

We also originally wanted to installed an air exchange system in the waiting areas and operating theatres to prevent the spread of airborne diseases. This would expell contaminated air and bring in fresh air. However there was not budget for this when we constructed the buildings. We have advised the building managers to install an air exchange system when there are funds for this.

Was there consideration of how to protect mosquitoes from getting bitten in the hospitals and reduce breeding sites for mosquito larvae?

Mosquito prevention was not a special consideration of the design. The windows were installed with netting which offers some protection. In one of the hospitals, pemba grass was laid in the interal courtyard but this is a bad idea as it attracts mosquitoes.

Can you describe the process for the landscape design around the hospitals?

There was little time to design these areas. External areas were not considered as this was one of the last stages of the construction process and at this point most of the budget had been used on the building. We did not design these spaces, instead each contractor was tasked to design the area.

What have you learnt from the process of designing and constructing the district hospitals that you are applying to the new PHCUs you are planning to build?

We have tried to improve the ventilation. We have increased the width of the windows from 1.5m to 1.8m. Also now wards have cross ventilation. Programmatically we increased the number of consultation rooms from 2 to 4 and we have introduced a post abortion room in the maternity section which the PCHUs did not have before. In addition we have increased the size of the medical store. We have also connected the pre-natal rooms to the deliver so patients do not have to use the main circulation. To reduce overheating, all laboratories are positioned to not have direct sunlight.